

Satisfaction as a mediator of the influence of service quality on the intention to reuse Grabfood Services in Denpasar City

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze customer behavior towards the GrabFood service in Denpasar, focusing on the impact of service quality on the intention to reuse and the role of customer satisfaction as a mediator. The research was conducted in Denpasar, an area with the highest level of smartphone usage and internet access in Bali (Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Bali, 2020). The object of this research is the population of Denpasar residents who have used GrabFood services. The population consists of residents of Denpasar who have used GrabFood, with a sample of 100 respondents selected through purposive sampling. Data collection was carried out through an online survey using a questionnaire, and data analysis was performed using classical assumption tests, path analysis, and Sobel tests.

The results of the study indicate that service quality has a positive and significant effect on the intention to reuse. The better the service quality of GrabFood, the higher the intention to reuse. Service quality also has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, meaning that the better the service quality, the higher the customer satisfaction. Furthermore, customer satisfaction is found to have a positive and significant effect on the intention to reuse, suggesting that customer satisfaction can drive the intention to use GrabFood services again in the future. Customer satisfaction also mediates the relationship between service quality and the intention to reuse. Therefore, it is recommended that GrabFood in Denpasar enhance service quality, speed up delivery, provide clear descriptions in the app, and offer attractive promotions to increase customers' intention to reuse GrabFood services.

Keywords: Service Quality; Intention to Reuse; Satisfaction; GrabFood; Denpasar

1. Introduction

The development of information technology in today's globalization era is advancing rapidly. The internet has become one of the advancements that continue to grow, helping and facilitating people's daily activities. The internet has also changed people's lifestyles to be completely online. The increasing sophistication of technology is also being used as a medium for online business. The shift in human economic activities, especially in shopping, has changed from face-to-face (offline) interactions to online activities on e-commerce and marketplaces, all through the use of smartphones (Ardianti and Widiartanto, 2019).

Transactions in e-commerce are projected to continue to increase every year. The Indonesian E-commerce Association (idEA) projects that e-commerce transactions in Indonesia will reach USD 77 billion or IDR 476.3 trillion in 2023, with an 18.77% year-on-year growth, and electronic money transactions will reach IDR 399.6 trillion (CNBC Indonesia). This presents an opportunity for business players to enhance and seize the chance to synergize in supporting economic activities through digital services. One of the rapidly growing digital services in Indonesia is food delivery services (Hariyanti, 2021).

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The dependence of Indonesian society on food delivery services has become unavoidable. According to a recent report from the research firm We Are Social, 19.85 million Indonesians utilized online food ordering services throughout 2022-2023. This figure increased by 16.5% year-on-year or 2.8 million people from the previous period (CNBC Indonesia). The total transaction for food delivery services in one year reached USD 1.2 billion or IDR 18.2 trillion. This figure grew by 26.3% from the previous year. On average, Indonesians spend USD 60.49 or IDR 918,000 annually on food delivery services via apps. One of the frequently used food delivery apps in Indonesia is GrabFood.

GrabFood is a food delivery service that can be ordered online through an app. This service entered Indonesia in 2016. GrabFood helps customers order food without taking much time, making it a practical and efficient service. GrabFood also offers a variety of restaurant choices with diverse menus. The payment system offered by GrabFood includes both cash payments and e-payment through one of its partners, OVO Payment. The delivery fee is calculated based on the distance between the customer and the restaurant partner.

Figure 1 Most frequently remembered food delivery services in Indonesia 2022

Based on the results of a survey conducted by Tenggara Strategic, Gofood received the highest score, with a percentage of 50 percent, as the most frequently remembered food delivery service application in Indonesia. ShopeeFood and GrabFood had percentages of 28 percent and 22 percent. Katadata Insight Center (KIC) also conducted the same survey in April 2021 with the results that 50 percent of survey respondents chose GrabFood as the most frequently used online food delivery service provider in the last three months. Then followed by GoFood (46 percent) and ShopeeFood (4 percent). Based on the data above, it can be seen that there is an indication of a decrease in the intention to use Grabfood as an online food delivery service. Consumers often carry out reuse activities because of the intention to use services that have been consumed because consumers have experienced the services provided by the seller. Sunu and Rahanata (2021) stated that the intention to reuse is the desire to use based on previous experience of using it. The intention to reuse is a decision planned by an individual to reuse a particular service, taking into account the situation that occurs and the level of preference. High reuse intention reflects a high level of consumer satisfaction when deciding to use a product or service. The intention to reuse a product or service is one indication that consumers are satisfied and confident with the product or service. Purba et al. (2020) define reuse intention as the desire of an individual to continue participating and using a system where the intention to reuse a system occurs after the customer has used it. The intention to reuse a service is an important thing for companies to pay attention to in order to see the customer's goals in meeting their needs or desires. Many companies compete by showing creative ideas to increase sales by using various methods such as presenting sophisticated features, discounts (price cuts), cashback, free shipping, special prices on certain dates, and others. This is done with the aim that prospective buyers do not get bored easily and fall in love with the company. One of the factors that influences the intention to reuse is service quality (Sukpa et al., 2015).

Table 1 Pre-Research Survey Data

No	Variables	Indicators	Statements	Yes	No	Total
1	Service Quality (X)	Order conformity	The order I received was as stated in the application.	11	9	20
		Order replacement guarantee	Grabfood is responsible for replacing losses when there is damage to the order.	6	14	20
2	Satisfaction (M)	Conformity to expectations	The quality of service provided by Grabfood is in accordance with what I expected.	8	12	20
3	Re-use intention (Y)	The desire to reuse	I plan to use Grabfood service again	9	11	20

Source: Primary Data processed, 2023.

Table 1 shows the results of the pre-survey: Eleven people agreed upon the statement regarding the quality of service consisting of order conformity. However, only six people agreed to the guarantee of order replacement. Eight people were satisfied with the quality of GrabFood services. Nine respondents stated that they planned to use GrabFood again to order food online. Service quality is an effort to fulfill customer desires and the determination of its delivery to match customer expectations (Tjiptono, 2014). Service quality is an important aspect of a company's development. Service quality greatly affects consumers because, with good service quality, the response back to the company will also be good (Adriani, 2019). The more positive the quality of service related to the use of GrabFood, the higher the intention of the community to reuse GrabFood services. This is in line with research conducted by Adriani and Warmika (2019) and Juliet (2020), which state that service quality has a positive and significant effect on the intention to reuse. The results of Sudarto's study (2022) stated that service quality has a direct positive and significant effect on the intention to reuse. Different research results were presented by Hon Liung and Tantri (2017) and Lemy et al. (2019), which stated that high levels of service quality and customer satisfaction do not affect the intention to reuse; this means that service quality does not guarantee customers to continue using a service.

Different previous research results strengthen the reasons for this study to further analyze the effect of service quality variables on the intention to reuse mediated by satisfaction, especially because the level of reuse of GrabFood services is still low. This study is expected to be a solution for GrabFood services in increasing competitive advantage and being able to compete with its competitors in the competition in the food delivery service industry in the future. In this study, customer satisfaction was chosen as a mediating variable because, as previously mentioned, the intention to reuse is closely related to a high level of customer satisfaction, and this satisfaction is formed because of good service quality. The selection of customer satisfaction as a mediating variable is also supported by several studies, such as Sudarto's (2022) study and Nurlaela Anwar and Ananda Wardani's (2021) study on service quality's effect on reuse intention with customer satisfaction as a mediating variable proving the positive influence of customer satisfaction in mediating between service quality and reuse intention. Based on several empirical facts and research gaps that have been described above, further research is still needed on the effect of service quality on reuse intention through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable.

2. Research methods

The research location is in Denpasar, especially for all Grabfood service users in Denpasar. The reason researchers chose Denpasar is because the intensity of people using smartphones and accessing the internet is the highest among all regencies/cities in Bali (Central Statistics Agency of Bali Province, 2020). The object of this study is customer behavior in the city of Denpasar related to the use of Grabfood services regarding opinions on service quality, intention to reuse and customer satisfaction.

The population in this study were people domiciled in the city of Denpasar who had used the Grabfood food delivery service. The number of indicators used was 10. so the number of respondents involved was in the range of 60-120 samples. This study will use 100 samples. The sampling method used in this study is non-probability sampling using the purposive sampling method. In this study, data collection was carried out using a survey method with a questionnaire tool distributed online to respondents. In this study, the analysis techniques used were the classical assumption test, path analysis, and the Sobel test.

Table 2 Research Variable Indicators

Variables	Indicators	Sources
Intention to Reuse (Y)	1. Desire to use the same service 2. Referring services 3. Making it the main choice 4. Looking for information	Miranda and Nurdasila (2020); Purba dkk (2020)
Customer satisfaction (M)	1. Performance perception 2. Conformity to expectations 3. Service Excellence	Panjaitan, J. E., and Yuliati (2016); Hardiana (2022); Reinarny (2019)
Quality of Service (X)	1. Driver appearance 2. Order condition 3. Order conformity 4. Driver availability 5. Schedule accuracy 6. Commitment 7. Fast service 8. Responsive service 9. Guarantee of order replacement 10. No unilateral cancellation 11. Providing customer adjustments 12. Order confirmation	Adriani (2019); Novianti (2018); Sudarto (2022)

3. Result and discussion

The classical assumption test was conducted with the aim of ensuring that the results obtained meet the basic assumptions in conducting regression analysis. The results of the classical assumption test processed with the help of SPSS software are presented as follows.

Table 3 Results of the Normality Test for Regression Equation 1

	Unstandardized Residual
N	114
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.065
Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on the data in Table 3, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) value is 0.065, while the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) value is 0.200. This indicates that the regression equation model 1 is normally distributed because the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) 0.200 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05.

Table 4 Results of the Normality Test for Regression Equation 2

	Unstandardized Residual
N	114
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.075
Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed)	0.157

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on the data in Table 4. it can be seen that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) value is 0.075, while the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) value is 0.157. This indicates that the regression equation model 2 is normally distributed because Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) 0.157 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05.

Table 5 Multicollinearity Test Results

Variables	Tolerance	VIF
Quality of Service	0.924	1.082
Satisfaction	0.924	1.082

Source: (processed data), 2025

The data in Table 5 show that the values of the Service Quality and Satisfaction variables have tolerance and VIF values of 0.924 and 1.082, respectively. This indicates that the regression equation model does not have multicollinearity because the Service Quality and satisfaction variables have a tolerance value greater than 10% and a VIF value less than 10.

Table 6 Results of Heteroscedasticity Test for Regression Equation 1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.723	0.182		3.963	0.000
Quality of Service	-0.023	0.048	-0.046	-0.490	0.625

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on Table 6, the Service Quality variable has a Sig. Value of 0.625, which is greater than 0.05. This means that the independent variables do not influence the absolute residual. Thus, equation model 1 does not contain symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Table 7 Results of Heteroscedasticity Test for Regression Equation 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.105	0.074		1.423	0.158
Quality of Service	-0.019	0.017	-0.100	-1.085	0.280
Satisfaction	-0.074	0.019	-0.358	-3.874	0.438

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on Table 7, the variables of Service Quality and satisfaction have Sig. Values of 0.280 and 0.438, respectively, which are greater than 0.05. This means that the independent variables have no influence on the absolute residual. Thus, it can be said that equation model 2 does not contain symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Table 8 Results of Path Analysis of Regression Equation 1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.028	0.310		6.538	0.000
Service Quality	0.249	0.082	0.276	3.048	0.003
R12 = 0.076	F Statistics = 9.288		Sig F = 0.003		

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on the results of the substructural path analysis 1, as in the data presented in Table 8, the structural equation is as follows

$$M = \beta_1 X + e_1$$

$$M = 0.276X + e_1$$

Table 9 Results of Path Analysis of Regression Equation 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.987	0.141		6.989	0.000
Quality of Service Satisfaction	0.719	0.033	0.729	7.590	0.000
	0.651	0.036	0.862	17.830	0.000
R22 = 0.758	F Statistics = 175.348		Sig F = 0.000		

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on the results of the substructural path analysis 2, as in the data presented in Table 9, the structural equation is as follows

$$Y = \beta_2 X + \beta_3 M + e_2$$

$$Y = 0.729X + 0.862M + e_2$$

Table 10 Standard Error Value Test Results

Test Result	Standard Error	Information
Pe1	0.961	Standard error of Service Quality variable e1
Pe2	0.491	Standard error of Reuse Intention variable e2

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on the calculation of the influence of error Pe1, the results of the influence of error Pe1 are 0.756, and the influence of error Pe2 is 0.650. The results of the total determination coefficient are as follows

$$R^2_m = 1 - (Pe_1)^2 - (Pe_2)^2$$

$$= 1 - (0.961)^2 - (0.491)^2$$

$$= 1 - (0.923) - (0.241)$$

$$= 1 - 0.222$$

$$= 0.778$$

Table 11 Results of the Total Determination Coefficient Test

Test Result	Determination Coef.	Information
R2m	0.778	The influence of independent variables on dependent variables in combination

Source: (processed data), 2025

The total determination value of 0.778 means that the Service Quality and Satisfaction variables influence 77.8 percent of the Reuse Intention variable. In comparison, the remaining 22.2 percent is explained by other factors not included in the model. Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, a significance level of F of 0.000 less than 0.05 was obtained, which means that the Service Quality variable and the Satisfaction variable have a simultaneous effect on the Reuse Intention variable. Based on the results of the analysis of the effect of Service Quality on Reuse Intention, a significance value of 0.000 was obtained with a beta coefficient value of 0.729. A significance value of 0.000 less than 0.05 means that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. This result means that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Reuse Intention. This is in line with the research results of Novianti et al. (2018) and Sitorus and Yustisia's research (2018), which stated that service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. However, Andalusi's research (2018) stated that service quality has a positive but not significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of Service Quality on satisfaction, a significance value of 0.000 was obtained with a beta coefficient value of 0.276. A significance value of 0.003 less than 0.05 means that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. This result means that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction. The results of this study are in line with the results of Rahayu's research (2022). This study shows that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction in the tourism industry in West Java. Simanjuntak and Siregar (2022) found that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction at Cafe Gaul Painan.

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of satisfaction on Reuse Intention, a significance value of 0.000 was obtained with a beta coefficient value of 0.862. A significance value of 0.000 less than 0.05 means that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. This result means that satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Repurchase Intention. The results of this study are in line with the results of Bahar and Sjahrudin's (2015) study, which found that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention. Rinaldi, R., and Arifin, Z. (2022) This study found that customer satisfaction has a positive effect on the intention to reuse the PLN Mobile application. Rizki, A. L., and Maulana, R. (2022) This study shows that service quality and customer satisfaction have a positive effect on consumer repurchase intentions at Hypermart. Nurhadi, M., and Suhendra, R. (2022) This study reveals that customer experience and trust have a positive effect on customer satisfaction, which in turn has a positive effect on repurchase intentions.

Figure 2 Final Path Diagram Model Validation

Table 12 Direct and Indirect Influence and Total Influence of Service Quality (X), Satisfaction (M), Reuse Intention (X)

Influence of Variables	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence Through Satisfaction (M) (b1 x b3)	Total effect
X-Y	0.729	0.628	0.904
X-M	0.276	-	0.276
M-Y	0.862	-	0.862

Source: (processed data), 2025

Based on the calculations that have been carried out, the Z value is 3.333 more than 1.96. These results state that the mediating variable, namely satisfaction, is considered to be able to mediate the effect of Service Quality on Reuse Intention at GrabFood Outlets in Denpasar City. The results of this study support the results of the study that customers are satisfied with the quality of service provided; they tend to be more loyal to the company or brand. Studies such as Sudarto's (2022) study and Nurlaela Anwar and Ananda Wardani's (2021) study found that satisfaction can mediate the effect of service quality on reuse intention positively and significantly.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion in the research that has been conducted, it can be concluded that Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Reuse Intention. This shows that the stronger the GrabFood Service Quality in Denpasar City, the higher the Reuse Intention. Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction. This shows that the stronger the Service Quality, the better the satisfaction. Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Reuse Intention. This shows that the better customer satisfaction with GrabFood Outlets in Denpasar City, the higher the Reuse Intention. Satisfaction is able to mediate the relationship between Service Quality and Reuse Intention. This shows that the satisfaction in the minds of customers towards GrabFood in Denpasar City can increase the influence of Service Quality on Reuse Intention. Some suggestions that can be conveyed in this study, it is recommended for GrabFood in Denpasar City to add drivers to deliver customer orders quickly, GrabFood Denpasar City to provide a clear picture of the application so that it is in accordance with customer expectations, and provide attractive promos in order to increase Reuse Intention.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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